

1 **The signal peptide peptidase-like 2A *Spp12a* is an essential component of a class I MHC code that**
2 **signals the presence of self.**

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8 The human utilizes multiple cellular based mechanisms to distinguish self versus non-self. We
9 demonstrate here the likely existence of a class I MHC code that serves in composition and quantity to
10 distinguish self versus non-self in a basic manner. Major components of the plasma membrane self code
11 included class I MHC molecules HLA-A, HLA-B and HLA-C. Other components of this plasma membrane
12 “self” code included immunoproteasome component *Psm8*. We describe the signal peptide peptidase-like
13 2A *Spp12a* as essential component of this class I MHC code that signals the presence of self.

14 Citations

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